

D2.2b. Innovation Readiness Level Report

Renewable Energy Technologies

Analysis of wind, solar and ocean power

July 2018

About this report

In the framework of REEEM project, three innovation readiness level reports will be developed on three different energy technology groups. The second report, presented in this document, is dedicated to renewable energy technologies. Five renewable energy technologies are selected and studied in this report, namely onshore and offshore wind, solar PV, tidal and wave. The technologies are from different sources of renewable energy and with different maturity status in order to provide a wider picture of the existing renewable technologies in the market.

This report will be complemented by the REEEM Technology and Innovation roadmap on renewable energy integration.

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About REEEM

REEEM aims to gain a clear and comprehensive understanding of the system-wide implications of energy strategies in support of transitions to a competitive low-carbon EU energy society. This project is developed to address four main objectives: (1) to develop an integrated assessment framework (2) to define pathways towards a low-carbon society and assess their potential implications (3) to bridge the science-policy gap through a clear communication using decision support tools and (4) to ensure transparency in the process.

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Summary

For more than two decades, the **European Union** has aimed to increase the share of renewable energy in the electricity industry. Long-term targets and effective policy measures were introduced in order to support the renewable energy growth. The results of this support could be seen in 30% share of renewable energy in the final electricity consumptions of Europe in 2017 when it was 12.4% in 1990. The targets oblige increasing the share of renewables in final electricity consumption to about 50% by 2030.

So far different types of **renewable energy technologies** have been introduced to the European electricity market. The technologies possess varied specifications and advantages, but not all have found the same positions in the market. Researchers and analysts often take varied technology maturity and development status as the reason for a successful access of a technology to the market. This report reveals that the technological maturity is not the only success factor.

This report explores the potentials and risks of renewable energy technologies in accessing the European electricity market, by using the **Innovation Readiness Level (IRL)** methodology. This methodology, developed by InnoEnergy,

assesses innovation readiness of a technology along 5 dimensions: technology readiness level, Intellectual property (IP) readiness level, market readiness level, consumer readiness level and society readiness level. The methodology explores factors and processes that are prerequisites for a successful technology development and access to a specific market.

This report assesses the IRL of 5 **renewable energy technologies**: onshore and offshore wind, solar PV, tidal and wave energy in the context of European electricity market. For the assessment of this report, a customized version of IRL tool, adapted for the REEEM project, is utilized. This customized version has been implemented in the last IRL report on energy storage technologies and has been improved afterwards based on the collected results.

The findings of this report suggest points in the **innovation processes** of the studied technologies which can effectively improve their competitiveness in accessing the European electricity market. The results provide suggestions for policymakers, investors and industries about the strengths and drawbacks of the innovation processes of the studied technologies.

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I. Introduction

1.1. The energy of the future: Renewable energy

The European Union (EU) is at the forefront of the global energy transition. Renewable energy technologies play a significant role in this transition. In 2017, the share of renewable energy in the final European energy consumption was about 17% and in the final European electricity consumption it was about 30% (see figure 1). The EU plans to increase this share to 32% in the energy market by 2030 [1], which requires increasing the share of renewables in the electricity market to about 50%.

The important role of renewable energy during the energy transition is highlighted in the Action 1 and 2 of Strategic Energy Technology (SET) plan communication. The SET plan helps to structure European and national research programmes and triggers substantial investments on common priorities in low-carbon technologies:

- Action 1: "to sustain technological leadership by developing highly performant renewable technologies and their integration in the EU's energy system"
- Action 2: "to reduce the cost of key technologies" (including renewable energy technologies)

Renewable energy in gross final energy consumption

The share of renewable sources in total EU-28 gross electricity consumption.

Figure 1 – Share of renewable energy in the European Union in 2017

Innovation has enabled renewable energy technologies to access the European electricity market and to compete with traditional sources of energy. Furthermore, innovation has resulted in the improvement of the technical features of renewable technologies and enabled them to reach an acceptable level of performance at a lower cost. Figure 2 shows that in 2017 technologies such as onshore wind or solar PV are cost-competitive when compared with fossil-fuel power generation. This cost competitiveness has motivated potential investors to engage in the renewable energy market and invest in these emerging technologies. In 2016, renewable energy accounted for 86% of all new EU power installations, 21.1 GW of a total 24.5 GW of new power capacity [2].

Source: IRENA Renewable Cost Database.

Note: The diameter of the circle represents the size of the project, with its centre the value for the cost of each project on the Y axis. The thick lines are the global weighted average LCOE value for plants commissioned in each year. Real weighted average cost of capital is 7.5% for OECD countries and China and 10% for the rest of the world. The band represents the fossil fuel-fired power generation cost range.

Figure 2 – Global LCoE from utility-scale renewable power generation technologies, 2010-2017[3]

In the last decades, technical features of renewable energy technologies have improved extensively in the electricity market. However, the technologies still face tenuous procedure and risks to access the market. In other words, technological innovation alone has not resulted in a successful access of renewable technologies to a market.

This report highlights that in order to fully understand the potential and risks of renewable energy technologies to access the European electricity market, all the parameters relevant that can influence innovation readiness of a technology should be studied. To do so, in this report the Innovation Readiness Level (IRL) methodology is utilised to access risks and potential of renewable energy technologies to access the European electricity market. Below IRL methodology and its historical development have been explained.

1.2. Technology development assessments tools: an overview

1.2.1. Technology Readiness Level (TRL)

In 1989 NASA introduced a systematic approach to studying the development of a technology, with the creation of the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) tool. The TRL describes the technology maturity level on a 0-9 scale, where 1 is the development of the idea in a laboratory and 9 represents the full technology readiness for deployment in the market. The tool assesses the technology maturity before its integration in the market, and studies asymmetries during the development process. The TRL tool is used widely in economic practice.

1.2.2. Demand Readiness Level (DRL)

To be successful, any new product or services needs to find its demands in the marketplace. This is because such analysis fails to consider innovation needs of different actors taking part in the market and the process of technology development [4]. Hence, in 2011 the concept of Demand Readiness Level (DRL) was developed in order to better understand and manage the process of technology deployment by hybridizing market pull and technology push approaches [5]. DRL has 9 levels and studies maturity of market demands identified by innovation actors. The levels range from identification of a need in a market to building an adapted answer to that need.

1.2.3. Innovation Readiness Level (IRL)

The Innovation Readiness Level (IRL) tool has been developed by InnoEnergy with the purpose of assessing the level of maturity of an innovative product, service or emerging business (i.e. startup and venture). The tool empowers the assessment of innovation potential of a technology, product or service by analysing all the dimensions that can influence its innovation process. The IRL extends earlier efforts that were focused on TRL and DRL and assesses a technology’s development along 5 different dimensions (Figure 3): Technology Readiness Level (TRL), Intellectual Property Readiness Level (IPRL), Market Readiness Level (MRL), Consumer Readiness Level (CRL), Society Readiness Level (SRL). Each dimension consists of several levels representing the technology readiness stage in that dimension. Successively, the IRL of a technology is assessed by considering the technology’s level in all the five dimensions. The dimensions are explained in the next chapter.

Figure 3 – InnoEnergy IRL tool

1.3. REEEM Innovation Readiness Level Methodology

The first customised version of IRL tool for the REEEM project was developed in 2017. This tool was used to evaluate and assess the development and deployment potential of energy storage technologies. In the REEEM IRL tool, the data is gathered by means of an extensive questionnaire. Each of the listed questions addresses one specific parameter or condition in the market under study (e.g., questioning the availability of alternative

technology in the market). The questionnaire includes binary or predefined answers to minimize the influence of biases and external opinions on the results. The answers are coded in order to report the results quantitatively (e.g., Yes=1, No=0). Next, the quantitative answers are summed and scaled in order to calculate the technology’s level in each IRL dimension. Note that, there is only one IRL questionnaire and that is been used for evaluating all technologies. There has been no weighting of the questions, meaning that all the questions within each IRL dimension were treated equally.

The obtained results are validated through literature studies and several interviews with experts who were involved in filling out the questionnaire. The overall IRL of a technology is assessed, by considering the technology’s level in all the five dimensions, namely TRL, IPRL, MRL, CRL, and SRL. A technology’s level within each dimension is reported as a number, and the IRL is reported as the sum of the technology’s level in all the dimensions (0-35). However, for understanding the IRL of a technology it is important to evaluate the technology’s potentials and risks to access the market along the five dimensions. In other words, the IRL cannot be understood as a standalone number, but rather as a description of a technology in all the five dimensions. For successful market penetration the importance of dimensions might differ among various technologies. Thus, the IRL provides only an overview of the current status of a technology without making any projection about its future development or deployment.

The results of the IRL assessment of a technology will be illustrated in a radar graph similar to the Figure 4. In this figure the recorded level of each dimension is scaled to 0-1 in order to make the comparison between the dimensions clearer. The noted numbers in the parentheses illustrate the minimum and maximum level of each of the studied IRL dimensions. The blue bar shows the status of the studied technology in each dimension of IRL.

Figure 4- Illustration of the results of the IRL assessment

Note, that for the IRL assessment of renewable energy technologies we used a revised version of the IRL tool. In this revision, both, questions and scales of the IRL tools’ dimensions, were improved based on the gained experiences during its first implementation on energy storage technologies. The aim was to collect more elaborate and representative data.

Below, all the REEEM IRL dimensions are explained:

TRL: this dimension is 9 levels and evaluates the maturity of a technology by exploring its development process from research to sale and certifications. In this process, TRL investigates the technology's objectives and studies its production and demonstration processes.

IPRL: this dimension includes 3 levels and assesses whether a technology could freely access and operate in the market, or its deployment is blocked due to established IPs and patents. Companies' knowledge about the existing patents in the market is evaluated and it is investigated how and if the companies cooperate together in respect to their IP rights. Data are obtained through several questions in the questionnaire and interviews with the experts.

MRL: this dimension includes 12 levels and investigates market parameters that affect need for the technology in the market. The analysis explores existing competition in the market, alternative technology solutions, or cooperation between the technology's value chain. When available, the future technology's market trend is studied and potential market size is explored in order to envision the technology deployment potential. The overall objective is to explore the market need for technology, and the road toward full commercialisation and successful deployment of the technology.

CRL: when end-users of a technology are different from its customers, the analyses of this dimension with 6 levels aims at exploring consumers' readiness and need for the technology. To exemplify, in the case of some European countries, the electricity customers are retailers, when consumers could be residential- or industrial-users (see Figure 5 for an overview of electricity consumers). The CRL estimates the consumers' willingness to engage in the technology development, analyse their needs, routines, resources and abilities. In addition, the CRL explores consumers' contributions to the technology deployment. The answers to the questionnaires and interviews with the experts indicate the significance and the role of consumers in the development and deployment of the technology in the market.

SRL: this dimension is 5 levels and evaluates the technology's stakeholders. Stakeholders does not only include consumers and customers, but also governments, NGOs, supply chains and any other authority involved in the process of technology development and deployment in the market. The assessment aims to identify if for each technology the stakeholders are identified, informed and involved in the process of technology deployment. Furthermore, through the findings of the interviews and the questionnaires, the concerns of the stakeholders are identified and it is explored if and how these concerns are tackled.

Figure 5- Final electricity consumption by sector in 2014 [34]

1.4.Context: Renewable Energy Technologies

This report assesses the IRL of five renewable energy technologies, namely onshore and offshore wind power, solar PV, tidal and ocean power. The selected technologies are chosen based on two reasons. Firstly, these technologies have the potential to play a significant role in the future European electricity industry and, secondly, they are at varying maturity levels. Therefore, by considering those technologies a more holistic understanding of the renewable energy market and of parameters that can influence the technologies’ development and deployment can be gained.

The IRL assessment of this report is focused on the European electricity market. This means that the studied technologies target the same groups of consumers and there are similarities between the stakeholders of these technologies. Accordingly, a part of the findings of the IRL assessment is comparable and transferable for all the technologies under study.

Figure 6 summarizes the methodological steps of this report.

Figure 6 – Overview of the methodology used for the development of the customized IRL tool for the REEM project

II. Innovation Readiness Level assessment: renewable energy technologies

II.1. Onshore wind power

Onshore wind energy is the most deployed type of renewable energy technologies in the European electricity market. Figure 7 illustrates the high share of wind power assumed in WindEurope’s central scenario¹ in the power mix of different EU-28 countries [6]. Figure 7 shows the cumulative share of onshore and offshore wind power, but in 2016 only about 15 GW out of the total capacity of 153 GW is offshore wind. This scenario projects this capacity to reach to 323 GW of which 253 GW onshore and 70 GW offshore wind.

Figure 7 – share of wind power in the EU-28 power mix according to WindEurope’s central scenario [6]

¹ In the Central Scenario, the EU would be able to power close to 30% of its electricity. The Central Scenario assumes that the EU meets its 27% renewable energy target in 2030 through the adoption of the Clean Energy Package proposals presented by the European Commission in November 2016. It also assumes significant progress in system integration, allowing a higher penetration of wind energy and other renewables as well as sufficient grid infrastructure to meet the EU’s 15% interconnection target.

The analyses within this report recorded the total number of 33.7 out of 35 for the IRL of onshore wind power. Figure 8 depicts the position of onshore wind on each of the IRL dimensions. The findings of each dimension are discussed separately below.

Figure 8- IRL of onshore wind power

Technology Readiness Level (Range 0 – 9):

Our analysis showed that onshore wind power is a mature technology with the TRL of 9. The technology and its applicability have been proven, the cost of technology is competitive and all the permitting and certification processes for the production and sale of this technology has been conducted. The European manufacturers of the wind turbines are identified and well-positioned in the global market.

Generally speaking, the onshore wind technology consists of three main parts: turbine, foundation, and structure. During the past years, an increase in the size of the turbine blades has contributed significantly to the technology’s performance and its associated cost reductions. Europe is among the leaders of wind turbine providers worldwide (Figure 9). While onshore turbine sizes were less than 1 MW in the year 2000, currently, they are larger than 2 MW. The projections for 2030 estimate onshore turbine sizes to reach about 3-4 MW [7]. Similar to the development of turbine sizes, onshore wind turbines’ foundation and structure have made improvement allowing the technology to improve its TRL level.

Figure 9- Onshore wind turbine suppliers and their global market share in 2017 [8]
 * European players are marked in green

Note, that although the onshore wind technology is at the level 9, some innovation cases and scenarios can still improve the technology. Improvements, for example, are possible by introducing new methods for Operation and Maintenance (O&M) or innovation in the technologies components (e.g. drivetrain). The full list of possible technological innovation is provided in the REEEM roadmap on renewable energy integration.

IP Readiness Level (Range 0-3)

This dimension recorded the number of 3. The existing knowledge on available IP rights in the market is extensive. Many businesses protect their product and services through IP rights. Figure 10 illustrates the evolution of patents related to wind power in Europe. This increasing number of patents give evidence on the technology advances that have been made in Europe during the last years. Interestingly, more than 85% of all the wind power patents in Europe are registered in 5 countries: Spain, Denmark, United Kingdom, France, Germany (Figure 11).

Our analyses also showed that there is sufficient cooperation among wind companies for sharing and utilizing the IP rights. This improves the technology position in the market.

Figure 10- the patent evolution of wind technologies in Europe (light blue wind energy and dark blue wind power) [9]
 *The database is filtered for available EU countries

Source: Deloitte for WindEurope

Figure 11 – the registered number of wind energy sector patents in the EU Member States and European Economic Area from 2006-2014 [10]

Market Readiness Level (Range 0-12)

This dimension recorded the number of 11.5, suggesting high acceptance for onshore wind technology in the market. Onshore wind technology answers an unsatisfied need in the electricity market by providing the clean and cheap source of electricity. The customers of the technology are identified, all the relevant parameters

related to political, social, technological and economical aspects of the technology are analysed. The technology is competitive and mature which reduces the risk to lose in the competition with other renewable energy technologies. There are several European players active along the supply chain. Onshore wind has competitive price and services and is accessible. All these factors strengthen onshore wind's position and enhance the MRL of this technology.

One parameter that affects negatively the MRL of onshore wind is related to instability of policies supporting onshore wind market, which lowers the interests of potential investors in this market. Besides, wind power development is faced with limited acceptance in some local markets due to its influence on the landscape. As the result of this low acceptance, the development of wind projects is associated with a long permission process in some markets, which lowers MRL of onshore wind technology.

Consumer Readiness Level (Range 0-6)

CRL of onshore wind technology recorded number 5.5. The analyses showed that the characteristics of onshore wind power consumers are identified. The technology fits into the cultural and environmental background of the European electricity consumers. In some regions, consumers are even actively involved in the wind power project development through community projects. This means that the consumers have the possibility to contribute to the technology development.

What lowers onshore wind CRL is based on wind power's variable electricity generation that calls for changes in consumers' routines for example through demand response. In addition, variable electricity generation can result in higher electricity prices at certain times of the year (e.g., during peak time).

Furthermore, development of wind technologies was not historically as cheap as it is today. Accordingly, their development was supported in the market through governmental subsidies. To illustrate, up to 15 years ago, in some European countries (e.g., Denmark and Germany) wind power investors received a feed-in tariff for a fixed price. However, the price represented the cost of technology 15 years ago, when it was much higher than today [11]. As the results, in some European countries, consumers are still paying for the cost of already installed wind power (or renewables in general)² reflected in the higher taxes that are added to their bills (Figure 12). This could be seen in Germany or Denmark with the highest rate of renewable technology penetration and high electricity prices (see [12]). Generally, the chance of increasing electricity prices for consumers is a reason for lowering the CRL of renewable energy technologies.

² For more information and reading please refer to the REEEM roadmap in renewable energy integration.

Figure 12 – Evolution of bill components 2008 – 2014 [37]

Society Readiness Level (Range 0-5):

SRL of onshore wind power recorded a number of 4.5. The stakeholders of the technology are identified and contribute to the development and deployment of onshore wind. In the electricity market, different European, national and local policies/initiatives support the onshore wind market. At the European level, directives are powerful tools to orient the market and drive further investments in onshore technologies. However, national and local decisions have a more direct influence on wind power development at a regional or country level.

What delimited SRL of onshore wind is first related to the end-of-life plan of onshore wind technology. Currently, there is some planning going on regarding recycling old turbines or repowering them through the replacement of the old parts of wind technology. Although these plans are becoming more financially attractive, they still need further development.

Besides, the increasing share of wind power in the electricity market is associated with a large share of fluctuating electricity generation in the market. The existing share of variable renewable power generation in Europe is small and thereby could be balanced using the available methods (such as grid interconnection between different European countries, intraday markets, and utilising energy storage technologies). Nevertheless, given the European targets for 2030 and 2050, share renewables will increase in the market and as the result, the need for balancing this variable electricity becomes more relevant. A list of potential solutions and technologies to balance renewable power production are listed in the REEEM roadmap on renewable energy integration.

Lastly, onshore wind power faces social resistance and limited acceptance in some regions. This is due to the influence of technologies on the landscape, or nature (birds’ migration). This resistance calls for the engagement of society in the development of wind power projects. A recent study has shown that 70% of project developers and cooperatives (of their sample) are engaged in activities related to society and public participation during the development of wind farm projects [13].

11.2. Offshore wind power

Offshore wind power refers to the installation of wind turbines on the seabed and far from the shore. In Europe, the first offshore wind farm, Vindeby, was installed in 1991 in Denmark. This wind farm was made of 11 small 450 kW turbines and had the capacity to generate 243 GWh of electricity. This wind farm was disassembled in 2017 after 25 years of operation. Vindeby might be considered as a small wind farm, it pioneered the development of offshore wind in Europe. Since then the offshore wind technology has been developed significantly in Europe. Currently, the two largest offshore wind farms worldwide are situated in Europe. These farms together meet the electricity demands of more than 2 million people. The largest wind farm, called the Array, is in England and consists of turbine sizes of 3.6 MW which are spread over 90 square kilometres (km²) area. The Array has the total capacity of 630 MW.

In order to assess the IRL of offshore wind technology, this report focused on the most common type of the technology available in the market now. This selection is based on the fact that IRL report provides an overview of the existing status of a technology in a market, which makes the assessment of new and emerging technologies more difficult. This means fixed-based foundation wind turbines with 6-8 MW turbine capacity. The results of the IRL assessment of the offshore wind technology is depicted in Figure 13. Below, detailed descriptions of the status of offshore wind in each dimension are presented.

Figure 13- IRL of offshore wind power

Technology Readiness Level (Range 0-9)

The TRL of offshore wind power recorded the number of 8.7, indicating the maturity of this technology. The technology is developed and fully tested in the relevant working environment. The application of the technology is foreseen and the technology demonstrates acceptable yield and level of productivity. The technology's manufacturing processes are established.

Innovation in offshore wind industry has resulted in improvement of sizes of offshore wind turbines. At the beginning of the 20th century, offshore wind turbine sizes were about 1.5 MW. At present, the turbines have

reached the capacity of 6-8 MW and the projection shows they have the potential to reach the capacity of 10-12 MW by 2030 [7]³.

Technological innovation in offshore wind power is not limited to turbine size, but also components, foundations as well as O&M methods. When it comes to offshore wind foundations, at the moment the foundations are mainly fixed bottom. Nevertheless, the share of other types of foundations is increasing in the market (see Figure 14).

Figure 14 - share of substructure types for offshore wind farms by the end of 2012 [14]

The foundation types and their basic specifications are explained below (Figure 15):

- **Monopile:** This foundation is most commonly used. It includes one pole which is possible to install up to 20-30 meters' depth. The pole is driven about 10-20 meters into the seabed.
- **Gravity-based foundation:** This foundation is currently the second commonly applied type of offshore wind power foundation. The gravity foundation consists of a large base made of steel or concrete which rests on the seabed. This foundation type is suitable for 30-50 meters' water depth.
- **Jacket foundation:** this type of foundation typically consists of corner piles that are connected with bracing with diameters up to 2 meters. The piles need to be driven into the seabed in order to gain adequate stability for the structure. This foundation could be installed at a water depth of 30-50 meters.
- **Tri-pile structure:** this foundation consists of three pile jacked structure, connected to the monopile on the upper part of the water. The foundation width and penetration should be adjusted according to the geological condition of the site. The length of the piles is variable between 60-90 meters. This foundation is suitable for water depth between 25-40 meters.

³ For further reading please refer to the REEM roadmap on renewable energy integration

- Tripod or Space farm:** This design is inspired by technology used in oil and gas industry. Each pile is driven about 10-20 meters into the seabed, depending on the soil condition. This foundation is applicable in sea depth up to 50-60 m.

Figure 15 – Different fixed based offshore wind turbine foundation(see [15])

At the moment, R&D efforts are focused on the development of new foundations, to enable access to far shore location with higher wind capacity. Development of floating foundations could resolve many of the limitations reducing TRL of this technology. The floating foundation allows access to high wind sites which in turn positively contribute to LCoE of offshore wind due to higher capacity factor. At the moment there are three main types of floating foundations for offshore wind turbines, namely spar-buoy, semi-submersible and tension leg platform which are explained below (Figure 16).

- Spar buoy:** in this type, a cylinder with low water plane area is ballasted to keep the centre of gravity below the centre of buoyancy. The foundation is fixed to the seabed by catenary or taut spread mooring lines with drag or suction anchors. In this model the design is simple, the cost of installing a mooring line is little, and there is a lower chance of critical wave induced motions. However, there is a need for heavy lifts vessels and the foundation is only applicable in water deeper than 100 meters.
- Spar-submersible:** in this type, a number of large columns (often 3) are connected by bracing or submerged pontoon. The column assures hydrostatic stability and the pontoon provides buoyancy. The foundation is connected to the seabed by catenary or taut spread mooring lines and drag anchors. This floating foundation type has benefits such as transportability by a draft below 10 meters or conventional tugs, or cheaper cost of mooring lines. On the other hand, they are more sensitive to critical wave-

induced motions, the tendency to use more material and have complex fabrication compared with other floating types.

- **Tension leg platform:** in this type, a central column and arms are connected to tensioned tendons which secure the foundation to the suction/piled anchors. This foundation has a lower mass, thus could be assembled onshore and dragged offshore. Unfortunately, this foundation is harder to keep stable during installation and transportation and it has high mooring cost. Besides, its high-frequency dynamic could affect turbines.

Based on NREL

Figure 16 – Different types of floating foundation for offshore wind turbines [44, p. 6]

In conclusion, the TRL can still be improved by lowering the technologies’ cost in order to be competitive with other renewable energy technologies. The need to reduce the offshore wind technology cost is also reflected in the Strategic Energy Technology (SET) plan's targets, as presented in Table 1.

Table 1- Set Plan targets for offshore wind

Reduce the levelised cost of energy (LCoE) at final investment decision (FID) for fixed offshore wind by improvement of the performances of the entire value chain	less than 10 ct€/kWh by 2020, less than 7ct€/kWh by 2030
Develop cost-competitive integrated wind energy systems including substructures which can be used in deeper waters (>50m) at a maximum distance of 50 km from shore with an LCoE of:	less than 12 ct€/kWh by 2025, less than 9 ct€/kWh by 2030

IP readiness Level (range 0-3)

IPRL of offshore wind indicated the level of 3. Companies active in the offshore wind market have a good knowledge of available IPs in the market. The number of wind power patents are increasing over the years in Europe (see Figure 10). Many businesses protect their technologies and create value from them through IP rights.

There is a cooperation between companies when needed in order to benefit from each other components and technologies. For example, when it comes to the sea-based structure and foundations, there is a cooperation between offshore wind developers and companies which were active in oil and gas industry and have extensive skills in the installation of foundation and structure in the ocean environment. This is a win-win situation since, on one hand, the companies involved in the construction of foundation in the ocean environment can expand their businesses into the wind industry. On the other hand, offshore wind power developers could benefit from existing IPs and knowledge in the market.

Market Readiness Level (Range 0-12)

The MRL recorded a number of 10.7. In 2017, there was 15.8 GW of cumulative offshore wind capacity in Europe (11 wind farms being built in Feb. 2018, adding 2.9 GW) [17]. This capacity represents about 13% of the annual EU wind energy market. By 2030, there would be 50-100 GW installed offshore wind capacity [6], which would meet 7% to 14% of the EU’s electricity demand in 2030 [6]. These numbers show that there are estimations available for the potential market size of offshore wind power in the European electricity market.

Furthermore, the need for the technology is acknowledged, as the European electricity market is deeming for a transition toward a sustainable and clean power industry. Customers of the technology are identified (e.g., utilities), a competitive value chain is created in Europe. In fact, the top 4 offshore wind turbine players are based in Europe (see Figure 17).

Figure 17- Global leading offshore wind power companies in 2017, based on market share [18]

There is extensive knowledge and analysis of the market parameters available. This includes the analyses of political, social, technological, and legal parameters. The analyses only show some limitations concerning societal parameters due to the technology's influence on both landscape (when is based close to shore) and ocean environment.

What in addition lowers the MRL of the technology is related to the high competition in the market that exists between offshore wind power and other renewable energy technologies. This competition is especially high with onshore wind power and solar PV. Moreover, the technology is associated with a high cost which increases the risk of investments in these technologies. Unstable renewable energy policies further intensify this financial risk.

Consumer Readiness Level (Range 0-6)

The CRL of offshore wind technology recorded number 5.3. The analyses of this dimension showed similar findings to the one of onshore wind because the consumers of the technologies are a similar group of people.

The CRL assessment showed that there is enough knowledge available in the market about consumers' characteristics including their geographical basis, income or energy consumption habits. The technology answers the need of consumers by providing them with a clean source of energy. The consumers are involved in the process of the technology development by sharing information regarding their consumptions patterns or engaging in community projects.

What delimits the technology's CRL primarily is based on the high cost of offshore wind projects that can create additional cost for consumers (being added to their electricity bills). This additional cost reduces the interests of consumers in offshore wind. Besides, offshore wind power is a variable source of energy which may call for changes in consumers' routine in order to be fully integrated into the electricity market. European energy consumers are aware of environmental issues and often willing to change their routine (e.g. through demand response). Though, in order to fully understand the impact of variable offshore wind (renewables in general) on the electricity market and evaluate cooperativeness of consumers first, a larger deployment of the technology is needed.

Society Readiness Level (Range 0-5)

The SRL of the technology recorded a level of 4.8 out of 5. The stakeholders of the technology are identified and are cooperating together. The European offshore wind supply chain is strong and players cooperate together in order to enhance the technology deployment.

The stakeholders' concerns about this technology are identified and mostly tackled. One of the concerns that lowers society interest in this technology is the unforeseen influence of the technology on the ocean environment. Additionally, emerging social resistance, known as "not-in-my-fishing-yard" or concerns about the influence of the technology on the landscape (when based nearshore) have resulted in the reluctance of certain parts of society. Recent developments have illustrated the limited influence of offshore wind technologies on the ocean. With the emergence of floating foundation and possibilities of installing the turbines far from shore, these societal concerns will be further reduced and the SRL of offshore wind technology will be enhanced.

Finally, intermittent electricity generation of offshore wind power can create concerns as the share of this technology grows in the market. This concerns can be tackled through several methods and market solutions, discussed in REEEM roadmap on renewable energy integration.

11.3. Solar PV power

Solar PV has been the type of energy source attracting most investments worldwide in recent years. In Europe, Solar PV with 104 GW installed capacity is one of the most deployed renewable energy technologies as of 2016. Having the possibility to be installed in different locations and sites, solar PV is a promising technology for the future European electricity industry. According to projections of IEA in 2014, the share of installed PV capacity in Europe will reach 196 GW by 2030 and 229 GW by 2050 [19]. In comparison, the IRENA report even estimates 270 GW of installed solar PV in Europe by 2030 in its ReMap scenario [20].

So far, there are different types of PV technologies available in the market. The technologies are made of different materials thereby have diverse technical characteristics. The existing PV technologies can be categorized into three main groups:

- **Crystalline silicon (c-Si):** These so-called first-generation PV systems (fully commercial and mature) use the wafer-based crystalline silicon (c-Si) technology, either single crystalline (sc-Si) or multi-crystalline (mc-Si). This technology entered the market around 50 years ago and is still the largest market share by far (about 93% market share in 2015, [21]). Commercial production of c-Si module began in 1963 [22] when the Japanese company Sharp Corporation installed 242 Watt on a lighthouse. The technologies are fairly mature with an efficiency of about 21-23% when the theoretical limit is 29% [21]. In spite of the technology maturity, cost reduction is possible through technological innovation and economy of scale in the production phase. Silicon is an abundant element in the earth's crust.
- **Thin-film:** the second commonly installed PV technology is thin-film, pertaining to the second-generation PV systems. It consist of three main groups: 1) amorphous Silicon (a-Si) (0.5% market share in 2015); 2) Cadmium-Telluride (CdTe, 4% market share in 2015); and 3) Copper Indium-Selenide (CIS) and Copper-Indium-Gallium-Diselenide (CIGS) (2.5% market share in 2015 [21], [22]). There is a long history of R&D on thin-films resulting in the production of thin-films in larger quantities. Thin-films potentially could offer a cheaper PV than c-Si PVs, but their efficiency would remain lower than c-Si. Thin-film could be packed into a flexible and lightweight structure and easily be integrated into the buildings (e.g., Building Integrated PV, BIPV).
- **Third generation PV technologies:** This type of technologies is in precommercial stage and still under development. There are four types of third-generation PV: 1) Concentrating PV (CPV); 2) Dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSC); 3) Organic solar cells; 4) advanced inorganic thin-film and novel and emerging solar cell concepts. While some of these technologies are to be commercialised, their success depends on the market share they manage to regain from the already established technologies.

In this report, we conducted the IRL assessment on the development of c-Si technology. This is because the technology is the most deployed type of technology in the market (with more than 90% share of the market) with a long development history for evaluation. The overall IRL assessment of c-Si PV technology recorded a number of 32.7 out of 35. Figure 18 shows the current status of the technology within each IRL dimension.

Note, that while below descriptions are mainly on c-Si technology, parameters influencing the development of other types of PV technologies, including thin-films for BIPV market, are also partly discussed.

Figure 18 – IRL of solar PV technology

Technology Readiness Level (Range 0-9)

The TRL recorded the number of 8.6, which gives evidence on the maturity of the technology. The technology has been developed and largely deployed in the electricity market. This technology benefited from extensive learning-by-doing due to its large deployment in the European electricity market. The technology indicates acceptable yield and production capacity, operates successfully in the relevant working environment and satisfies its application objectives.

What delimits the TRL of this technology is related to its high cost which is exacerbated by the low technology efficiency. This calls for the development of the technology in order to find substitute material or manufacturing processes that could reduce the technology cost. Improving the efficiency of this technology will also reduce the technology’s cost by increasing its production capacity. The SET plan targets presented in Table 2 provide a good overview of the plans for improving solar PV technologies.

Table 2 - SET plan targets for solar PV

Major advances in the efficiency of established technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase PV module efficiency by at least 20% by 2020 compared to 2015 levels; - Increase PV module efficiency by at least 35% by 2030 compared to 2015, including with the introduction of novel PV technologies.
Reduction of the cost of key technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduce turn-key system costs by at least 20% by 2020 as compared to 2015 - Reduce turn-key system costs by at least 50% by 2030 compared to 2015 with the introduction of novel, potentially very-high-efficiency PV technologies manufactured at large scale.
Further enhancement of lifetime, quality and sustainability and hence improving environmental performance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maintain proven system energy output per year at least 80% of the initial level for 30 years by 2020 and for 35 years by 2025; • - Minimize life-cycle environmental impact along the whole value chain of PV electricity generation, and increase the recyclability of system components (in particular: of modules); - Perform focused research and apply & progress eco-design requirements in preparation of implementing measures supporting maximum energy yield (kWh/kWp) and lowest life-cycle environmental impact.
Major advances in manufacturing and installation:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Make available GW-scale manufacturing technologies that reach productivity and cost targets consistent with the capital cost targets for PV systems; - Develop PV module and system design concepts that enable fast and highly automated installation, to reduce the installation costs of both ground-mounted arrays and PV building renovation solutions, by 2020.

The TRL for other types of technologies, such as thin-film PV technology is lower than c-Si technologies. For thin-film, limited technology efficiency, its low deployment rate and high cost are the main reasons for delimiting technology's access to the market.

IP Readiness Level (Range 0-3)

IPRL of c-Si technology recorded number 3. Companies active in this industry possess enough knowledge of IP rights that influence their project development. There is cooperation between companies in order to benefit from existing IP rights for further development of the c-Si market. The emerging number of patents (Figure 19) illustrates advances that have been made.

Figure 19 – the patent evolution of Photovoltaic technology [9]
 *The database is filtered for available EU countries

For novel PV technologies, the market is emerging and further establishment of IP rights could allow creating value for these technologies.

Market Readiness Level (Range 0-12)

MRL of solar PV recorded the number of 11.4. The need for the technology is identified, actors are positioned across the value chain and support the development of the market. The goals and targets for the development and deployment of solar PV in Europe are set in order to increase the share of technology in the market. In 2016 there is 104 GW of total accumulated Solar PV capacity installed in Europe. In IRENA Remap scenario this capacity can reach 270 GW by 2030 [20].

Different market parameters currently support the deployment of solar PV technologies. Examples of these parameters are supportive policy mechanisms (feed-in-tariff, tax reduction), positive society perspective on solar PV, community projects resulting in a larger engagement of consumers in the market, availability of funding for investment projects and smooth permitting procedure. The services around this technology are reliable, but this depends partly on the project developer. Our analyses also showed that the main reasons behind investments decision of investors in this market are identified and major barriers are resolved.

What delimits the MRL of this technology is the high competition that exists between c-Si technologies and other renewable energy technologies (including other PV technologies). This competition is intensified because of the higher price of PV technology when compared with other alternative options.

Furthermore, policy mechanism and subsidies that support solar PV technologies have been changing their types and amount through the years. These changes lower MRL of PVs by demotivating potential investors. The dependency of the technology on natural resources and lack assurance about the actual revenue of this technology further increases financial risks of PV projects.

Consumer Readiness Level (Range 0-6)

The CRL of the technology recorded number 5.3, indicating the high readiness of European consumers for the deployment of solar PVs. Characteristics of consumers are identified and their needs and desires are known. Our analyses show that the consumers have the capacity and interest to engage in the development of the technology. In fact, solar PV is among few energy technologies that allows both large and small-scale consumers to produce power for their own consumptions or delivery to network [23]. In recent years, the development of community projects in Europe has positively contributed to the better engagement of consumers in the market.

Moreover, consumers by sharing their data can contribute to the integration of solar PV technologies in the market. Most of the companies have already plan to engage consumers, for example by asking the consumer to share data during peak times in order to improve their services by improving the technology's performance (for example by enhancing the efficiency of inverters).

Although advancements have been made, a number of factors still lower the CRL of solar PV technologies. Firstly, similar to other renewables, the integration of a large share of variable power generated by solar PVs can influence the routines of consumers. In order to improve CRL of solar PVs, comprehending how and by which extent the consumers' routines will be affected is helpful. Secondly, similar to other renewable energy technologies, the price of electricity has increased in some countries due to subsidies introduced for solar PV projects (see, [24]). This high cost has affected consumers' perspective in some regions about renewable technologies in general.

Society Readiness Level (Range 0-5)

SRL of c-Si PV technology recorded the number of 4.5. The stakeholders of this technology are identified and their views and concerns are explored. Additionally, governments further influence the SRL of solar PV positively through supportive legislation, subsidy or tax reduction.

Furthermore, solar PV benefits from a high rate of social acceptance. To illustrate, the analysis in Germany showed 72% of acceptance for solar PV installation in the neighbourhood of consumers, while this rate is only 57% for wind energy [25]. In the UK the level of support for solar energy is even higher and is close to 80% [26].

However, many stakeholders are concerned about the large share of variable electricity in the market. This calls for the introduction of methods and measures that can balance the variable renewable electricity production. This, for example, is possible through larger deployment of storage technologies⁴. Furthermore, solar PVs consist of raw materials which create concerns about availability and access to resources and prices of these materials. To tackle these concerns, there are plans for the development of recycling facilities or improvement of material usage in technologies. Though, the slow accomplishment of these plans has negatively influenced the SRL of solar PVs.

Lastly, our analyses showed that different European, national or local policies/initiatives contribute to the deployment of solar PV technologies in the market. The analyses showed that on the European level, the European Commission provides a good direction for the overall development of the solar market. On the national

⁴ For a complete list of available methods please refer to the REEEM roadmap on energy storage applications

level and in different member-states, supportive policies aim at accelerating the development of the PV market. At the local level, measures such as community project and smooth permission process aim to increase the potential of PV technologies in accessing the market.

11.4. Tidal power

As the result of the relative moon and sun movement to earth, oceanic tides are produced. These gravitational forces create a periodic vertical movement of oceans and seas, known as the tidal range. The tides are accompanied by incoming and outgoing horizontal flow of water which referred to as tidal current or stream. When properly harnessed, tides provide a great source of energy. The highest potential of tidal energy is typically located in areas with significant tidal range [27]. The UK hosts about 50% of Europe's tidal energy capacity (more than 10 GW of capacity) [28].

The development of ocean energy in Europe goes back to 1966 when a 240 MW tidal project was built in La Rance, France. Generally speaking, there are two different groups of tidal energy technologies available in the market. The technology groups are:

- **Tidal range:** tidal range technology is based on the height differences between high and low tides to generate power. Tidal turbines, for example, located in a barrage, are used for this power generation. It can offer a wide range of capacity.
- **Tidal stream** [29]: in this type, the turbines are installed on the seabed or float on the surface and use from the flow of the currents to produce electricity. Tidal stream devices function similar to wind turbines, converting kinetic energy into electricity. Between 2006-2013 more than 40 types of tidal stream technologies were introduced into the market. The differences between these technologies are based on the turbines position (both horizontal and vertical). In the last three years, several big companies (e.g., ABB, Alstom) have invested in tidal stream meaning that the market is not only driven by entrepreneurs.
- **Hybrid technology** including a mixture of these two categories is also an option.

There are four main components in most of the tidal technologies: 1) A *barrage* which is used to convert ocean energy to electricity in tidal range technology; 2) A *tidal turbine* (vertical or horizontal) which is used to transfer the kinetic energy of stream to electrical energy; 3) *Mooring line* or foundation that keeps a tidal technology in place when there is a need for supporting lines or foundation. Among the existing projects and concepts currently, 56% uses rigid connection (mostly seabed), 36% uses moorings, and 4% monopiles [30]; 4) *Electrical cable* that connects the ocean energy technologies to the shore. They are normally installed in a trench at the seafloor, below the beach on shore.

So far, different types of tidal energy technologies have been developed, using one of the above-mentioned principals and components. This report identified this variety and lack of convergence as one of the reasons for the slow development of the tidal energy market and lower IRL of tidal technologies when compared with other technologies, like wind and solar, studied in this report. This slow development, in consequence, attracted less attention and less investments which resulted limited development of tidal technologies.

As mentioned, there are several types of tidal technologies available in the market. These technologies are at different development and maturity level. The assessments of this report represent an average status of tidal technologies. The discussion presented in each dimension aims at shedding light on particularities of different available tidal technologies in the market. Figure 20 shows the IRL status of tidal energy along the five studied dimensions. The overall IRL recorded the number of 25 out of 35. The TRL and MRL were identified as the weakest dimensions of the technology's IRL.

Figure 20- IRL of tidal power

Technology Readiness Level (Range 0-9)

The TRL of tidal technology recorded number 7. Basic principles of the tidal technology are identified and its application is foreseen. The physical and operational conditions of the tidal technology are known, and its different elements are developed and tested. The characteristics of the technology in term of performance and efficiency are known. Currently, most of the tidal technologies are being tested as a prototype in the relevant operating environment in order to prove their functionality. Between 2014-2016, the tidal energy sector has made a significant progress toward commercialisation. Key technology developers, such as Atlantic Resource cooperation or OpenHydro and several other projects in the UK, have created the conditions for the accelerated project development.

After completion of the tests and indicating the full functionality of the tidal technology, the next challenge would be to enhance its performance and reduce its cost through large deployment in the market. Table 3 shows SET plan targets for 2030 indicating the aim to reduce the technologies’ cost.

Note, that the above discussion is valid for general status of tidal technologies in the market. In some specific cases such as barrage in France or the technology of tidal resource of Atlantis Resources, the TRL level is higher and closer to level 9. Figure 21 shows the status of different tidal technologies with the different functioning principals. As it is illustrated in this figure, even in one principal the available technologies are at different maturity level. The uncertainty about which type of tidal technology and by when would reach the full commercialization is what lowers the TRL of this technology. The high cost of technologies at this stage make this process more uncertain.

Table 3 - SET plan targets for Tidal power

Development of cost-competitive ocean energy technologies with high market potential for Europe.	- The LCoE for tidal stream energy should be reduced to at least 15 ct€/kWh in 2025 and 10 ct€/kWh in 2030.
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Figure 21 - Range of TRL for different tidal power devices available* [31, p. 4]

* Range of testing for tidal energy devices. Blue bars refer to technology with significant progress in 2016. Red bars indicate technology with no considerable update/progress in 2016. Shaded bars indicated ongoing testing. The length of bar indicates the range of TRL attempted. The yellow dot indicates the maximum achieved TRL.

IP Readiness Level (Range 0-3)

The IPRL records number 2. The tidal energy market is new and therefore tidal companies tend to protect their technologies and expand their business through the development of IP rights. The number of patents is increasing, which illustrates the advances that have been made in the development of ocean industry, including tidal technologies (Figure 22).

Tidal companies cooperate with other companies active in the ocean environment when it is beneficial for their business. This is the case when tidal technology developers cooperate with companies specialised in the construction of foundations and structure below the ocean surface. These companies have gained years of experience through the completion of projects for the offshore wind or oil and gas industry.

As discussed, so far different types of tidal technologies are introduced into the market. Our analyses suggest that for the market to reach maturity and for an accelerated development of tidal technologies, a dominant

technology will emerge through convergence. In the light of the established IP rights, this convergence could be more difficult and create issues for the development of the market, without further cooperation between companies active in this market. This is what has been reflected in IPRL of 2 out of 3 for this technology.

Figure 22 – the patent evolution of ocean energy [9]
 *The database is filtered for available EU countries

Market Readiness Level (Range 0-12)

The MRL assessment recorded level 7.3 out of 12. The existing gap in the market is identified. The tidal power could play a big role in the market by providing a predictable renewable source of power. The predictability of tidal power makes this technology a great option for the balancing of the European electricity system. The predictability of tidal power sources creates a competitive advantage for tidal technology when compared with other renewable power sources. So far, different methods and technologies, such as the deployment of energy storage, are introduced to the electricity market to enhance its flexibility. However, in order to balance the power system effectively and efficiently, a combination of different solutions is needed.

Our MRL analyses show that the technology’s customers are identified. Examples of customers are utilities, grid operators, island communities or oil and gas industry. Several market parameters positively influence the development of tidal power market. This includes 1) policies and legislation that influence the technology development through both pull and push policies or investments in technology R&D, 2) society acceptance of the tidal technology or 3) the developed value chain of the tidal technology in Europe. Europe, in fact, more than half of the tidal energy companies worldwide are located in Europe (Figure 23). The technology developers currently in the market use contracting for the manufacturing of tidal technologies’ components (since the technologies are still at the commercialization stage).

Figure 23- distribution of tidal energy developers in the world [31]

What delimits the MRL of the tidal technology is the technology immaturity and high project risk. Besides, competition between tidal technologies and other renewables further limit MRL for tidal technologies. Although tidal power is a predictable source of power, yet its high price and slow technology development exacerbate competition between tidal and other renewables.

Furthermore, accessibility of tidal energy resources is another issue influencing MRL of tidal technologies. As discussed, there are extensive resources of tidal energy available in waters around the UK. But, in the time of Brexit operationalization of European tidal projects have been questioned.

Consumer Readiness Level (Range 0-6)

The consumers of the tidal technologies are different from the customers. The CRL of technology recorded number 4.5. The consumers of the technology are identified (electricity consumers) and their energy habits are known. The technology can satisfy the need of consumers by providing them with a clean and predictable source of electricity.

What reduces the CRL level of the tidal technology is the limited development of this technology in the market, which is associated with its low performance and high cost. Due to this limited development, the technology yet cannot be tested using consumers' experience and adapted based on their needs or desires. Additionally, similar to other renewables, a large share of tidal power is coupled with an increase in the share of variable electricity. This may call for changes in the consumers' routines.

Society Readiness Level (Range 0-5)

The SRL of tidal energy recorded the number of 4 out of 5. The stakeholders of the technology are identified and are engaged in the process of technology development. Many stakeholders find tidal energy technologies to be an opportunity to improve their own position in the energy market. Governments invest in tidal energy technology in order to accelerate sustainable energy transition in Europe. The society tends to have a positive attitude towards the development of tidal power due to its limited influence on the landscape or ocean environment.

Utilities are engaged in the development of tidal energy and have invested in different tidal development projects in order to strengthen their position in the market. Many of these projects have been already terminated and utilities are more reluctant nowadays to invest in these technologies. The main reason for this reluctance is the lack of technologies' success and their slow development process. The cooperation between utilities and tidal energy developers is improving the development process of the tidal technology in more recent years.

Furthermore, suppliers are engaged in the development of the tidal technology as both small and big suppliers can make revenue if the technology becomes successful. Incorporation in the tidal energy market provides suppliers with a unique opportunity to expand their business in the renewable energy market.

EU laws support the development of tidal technology and aim to bring the technologies closer to a large deployment. The role of national government is currently significant because it is often up to the national government to develop regulations enabling large technology deployment.

What reduces the SRL of the technology is the tedious development history of ocean energy industry, which makes it difficult for any stakeholders to commit financially to the tidal energy industry. Besides, there are some segments such as the fishing industry that is concerned about the technology development in the ocean environment, although the society, in general, evaluates the development of tidal technologies positively.

11.5. Wave power

Waves are generated on the ocean surface with wind blows and are a function of temperature and pressure difference. Wave energy converters generate energy from the movement of waves and can be located flexibly onshore, nearshore or offshore [27]. Wave energy has the potential to meet up to 10% of global electricity demand by 2050 [32]. Although wave energy is an intermittent source of energy, its combination with other renewable power sources (e.g., offshore wind technology) has shown the potential to provide a more balanced generation curve.

Similar to tidal power, there are different types of wave energy technologies available in the market. The diversity of these technologies implies lack of market convergence and technology immaturity. Wave technologies could be installed onshore, nearshore and offshore, each requiring certain technical specifications.

- **Onshore devices:** In onshore wave energy, devices are mounted on a natural rock or breakwater. On the positive side, these devices are close to the utility network and benefit from low cost and easy maintenance. However, due to their proximity to the shore, the potential resources to be captured are less than for the other types of wave energy.
- **Nearshore devices:** These devices are located in shallow water areas and are fixed to the seabed with pinned pile foundation or gravity mass. This type of wave energy has the advantage to provide a suitable stationary base against which an oscillating body can work. Nearshore devices still have lower potential energy yield when compared with offshore wave energy.
- **Offshore devices:** In this type of wave energy, devices are located in deep water. The devices are tethered to the seabed using tight of slack moorings mass. In offshore areas, the potential yields are much greater but the cost of wave projects is higher due to the complication of construction and O&M.

Most of wave energy technologies include the following components [33]: 1) The main *structure* and *mover* that harness the wave energy; 2) *Moorings lines* or *foundation* which keep the structure in place; 3) The *power take-off* in order to convert mechanical energy into the electrical energy 4) The *control system* which optimise the performance of the technology in different operating conditions.

The assessment of this report recorded the overall IRL score of 24.2 for wave energy out of 35 (Figure 24), slightly lower than the recorded IRL score for the tidal power. The detailed descriptions of each dimension are provided below.

Figure 24- IRL of wave power

Technology Readiness Level (Range 0-9)

Development of wave energy technologies in the market is behind the tidal energy technologies, the TRL of wave technology is at the level of 5.3. There are more than 100 different types of pilot projects available around the world for wave technologies, but only a handful of technologies are close to the commercialization (see Figure 25) [33]. Figure 25 illustrates there are different types of wave technologies available in the market and the technologies follow different functioning principals and are at different TRL. One reason for this technology variety is the existence of different approaches for harnessing the wave power. Another reason is immaturity of the technology, absence of a dominant design and as the results the technology high cost. Table 4 illustrates SET plan targets suggesting cost reduction of wave technologies.

Figure 25 - Range of the TRL for available wave energy devices* [31]

* Range of TRL for wave energy devices. Blue bars refer to technology with significant pro-gress in 2016. Red bars indicate technology with no considerable update/progress in 2016. Shaded bars indicated ongoing testing. The length of bar indicates the range of TRL attempted. The yellow dot indicates the maximum achieved TRL.

Wave energy technologies still need additional R&D effort in order to assure viability and survivability of their key components in the harsh ocean environment. A full-scale prototype is also needed to make sure all the key components of the technologies work together.

Another reason lowering TRL of wave technologies is that the development of wave energy has been slower than the initial projections. This slow development has further questioned the actual potential of wave technologies and made the market hesitant to invest in wave technologies. In recent years there has been some improvement in the wave technologies (e.g., Aquamarine Power and Pelamis Wave Power) and their success has increased the promises of wave power technologies [31].

Table 4 - SET plan targets for wave power

Development of cost-competitive ocean energy technologies with high market potential for Europe.	- Wave energy technology should follow the same pathway and reach at least the same cost targets maximum 5 years later than tidal energy: 20 ct€/kWh in 2025, 15 ct€/kWh in 2030 and 10 ct€/kWh in 2035.
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IP Readiness Level (Range 0-3)

IPRL of the technologies recorded the number of 2.3, similar to tidal technology. Our analyses illustrated that, currently, there are no remarkable issues related to IP rights in the wave market. The increasing number of patents in ocean energy, as shown in Figure 22, illustrates advances that have been made in ocean technologies.

Our assessments show that wave project developers have good knowledge basis of the available IP in the market. They possess adequate information and have made suitable planning to create value for their products through IP right. Similar to tidal energy, companies active in the development of structure and foundation for wave technologies are experienced and well established. These companies have already operated in offshore wind or oil and gas industry.

What delimits the IPRL of the technology is limited cooperation between different technology developers which restrict faster development of the technology and its learning-by-doing in the market. While limited cooperation currently is not a big issue in the market, the emergence of a dominant technology could increase the risk of conflict between IPs.

Market Readiness Level (Range 0-12)

MRL of wave technologies recorded the number of 7.9. The need in the market is recognized and the potential customers of the technologies are identified. Examples of customers could be utilities who are interested in new technologies that allow them to expand their services; island communities with limited access to grid connection; agriculture industry to replace their diesel generation, or oil and gas industry to find clean energy for running their equipment.

What creates competitive advantages for wave technologies in the market is their potential to contribute to a balanced renewable power generation (when coupled with other renewable energy sources such as offshore wind). The value chain of the technology in the market is identified and positioned in the market. As shown in Figure 26, about 60% of wave energy developers are based and active in Europe. The developers often use contracting for manufacturing and installation of (prototype) technologies.

Figure 26- distribution of wave energy developers in the world [31]

What limits the MRL of wave technologies is primarily owed to the limited development of wave technologies which creates doubts about the actual potential of the technology. This slow development also makes any projections about the future market size or trend uncertain.

Furthermore, the technology deployment potential in the market is associated with risk of high competition 1) between different types of wave technologies and 2) with other renewable power technologies. Although wave technologies have competitive advantages in comparison with other renewables, they suffer from lack of development. This prevents them from finding a better position in the electricity market, at the moment.

Consumer Readiness Level (Range 0-6)

When it comes to wave energy, the CRL recorded the number of 4.8 out of 6. The characteristics of consumers of the technologies are identified and their need is recognized. The consumers of wave power technologies are identical to other renewable power technologies' consumers, particularly tidal technologies. This explains the similarity of the CRL assessments' results in this report.

What delimited the CRL of the technology is that consumers have currently other alternative renewable technologies with higher performance and lower price to satisfy their need. Therefore, when given an option, consumers opt for other renewable energy sources than wave technologies.

Additionally, like for other renewables, a large share of wave power in the electricity market may require changes in the consumers' routines, for example by calling for better demand response. High awareness of European consumers about the environmental issues can facilitate expected changes in their routines.

Society Readiness Level (Range 0-5)

The SRL of wave technology recorded number 4.1 out of 5. The stakeholders of the technologies are identified and are engaged in the development and deployment of wave technologies. Governments and official authorities are supporting the technology development in order to find solutions for tackling climate challenges. Utilities contribute to the technology development in order to diversify their power generation portfolio and find power sources to substitute their fossil-based generation.

European, national and local authorities support the development of wave technologies in some ways. Our analyses show that the targets and the planning for the development of wave technologies are set at the EU level. National governments support the implementation of national projects, and local communities allow and certify a permission for project development.

What lowers SRL of the technologies is related to the concerns regarding the influence of the technology on the ocean environment. Although so far no potential harmful effects are indicated, there is a need for further research and analysis to assure lack of environmental side effects. Limited deployment of technologies and historical data exacerbated existing concern about the environmental effect of wave technologies. Similar to tidal energy, fishing industry is the most concerned sector regarding the development of wave power in the ocean environment.

III. Conclusion: Comparative analysis of IRL of renewable energy technologies

This report evaluated the innovation readiness of 5 renewable energy technologies to access the electricity market, by utilizing the IRL methodology. This methodology assesses development and deployment level of a technology in a specific market along the five dimensions of TRL, IPRL, MRL, CRL, and SRL. The analysed renewable energy technologies are onshore and offshore wind, solar PV and wave and tidal technologies and the targeted market is the European electricity market. This report explores points in innovation processes of these technologies that can enhance their competitiveness in accessing the market. Table 5 provides an overview of the IRL assessment results.

Table 5 – Summary of the IRL assessment of the studied renewable energy technologies*

Technology \ Dimension	Onshore wind	Offshore wind	Solar PV	Tidal	Wave	Maximum score
TRL	9.0	8.7	8.6	7.0	5.3	9
IPRL	3.0	3.0	3.0	2.3	2.3	3
MRL	11.5	10.8	11.4	7.3	7.9	12
CRL	5.5	5.3	5.3	4.5	4.8	6
SRL	4.7	4.8	4.5	4.0	4.1	5
<i>IRL (SUM)</i>	<i>33.7</i>	<i>32.5</i>	<i>32.7</i>	<i>25.0</i>	<i>24.2</i>	<i>35</i>

The analyses of this report found a similarity between a number of parameters that influence the renewable technologies' potential to access the market. The parameters are related to market, consumer or society. This similarity indicates that improving any of these parameters can positively enhance IRL level of all renewable energy technologies. For example, the analyses of this report found out that a larger share of variable power sources in the European electricity market may call for changes in consumers' routine (e.g., through demand response). Finding approaches that balance this variable power or facilitate changes in consumers' routines allow better deployment of all types of renewable technologies. In other words, the findings of this study suggest that the improvement in the IRL of one renewable technology is likely to have more a positive influence on the IRL of other renewable energy technologies.

However, it should be also noted that that a higher IRL level of renewable technology (e.g., offshore wind) can create barriers for the development of other and more immature types of renewables (e.g., wave technologies). This is because, immature renewable technologies often loose in competition with mature technologies, when competing for similar investment and funding opportunities. This rising competition could be handled through further development and advancement of support mechanisms targeting only immature renewable technologies.

Below the similar parameters that are influence IRL of all the studied renewable energy technologies are listed:

- All the technologies need to compete with other available alternative technologies in the market. Renewable technologies need to compete with both conventional resources and other types of

renewable energy technologies. For more immature and expensive types of renewable energy technologies, such as tidal and wave power or offshore wind energy, this competition is more intense.

- Changes in type and duration of policies supporting the renewable energy market increase the risk of investment in renewable energy technologies and lower the interests of potential investors.
- Onshore and offshore wind power and solar PV all recorded the TRL of almost 9. In spite of the technologies' maturity, their cost and performance could be improved in the market through their larger deployment (economy of scale), enhanced manufacturing processes or R&D efforts (improving technologies efficiency or material usage).
- Supporting renewable energy market is often coupled with extra cost for consumers as they need to pay for the financial support provided by the government (see Figure 12). This is particularly true since renewable technologies were more expensive 15 years ago and still consumers are paying for that cost. This higher cost in some regions has decreased the electricity consumers' interests in the renewable technologies.
- Variable power generation of the renewables may affect the routines of electricity consumers, by calling for better demand response. For some of these consumers, changing the routines would be more burdensome than others.
- Limited understanding of the actual influence of renewables on the environment has created social concerns about the deployment of renewable technologies. Examples of these concerns are the influence of wave and tidal technologies on ocean biodiversity or wind technologies on bird migrations.
- The share of raw material usage in renewable technologies questions the availability of resources, sustainability of renewable energy technologies, and result in a higher technology cost due to materials' price volatility. Lack of recycling facilities exacerbates this issue.
- All studied renewables indicated an acceptable level of IPRL. Active companies share knowledge and information and cooperate together in order to benefit from each other's knowledge and experience.

The analyses illustrated notable differences on the TRL of the studied renewable technologies:

- Onshore wind power is the most developed and advanced type of renewable power technology with the TRL level of 9.
- Offshore wind power recorded the number of 8.7 which indicates the maturity of the technology. Further cost reduction can improve the position of the technology in the market.
- Solar PV recorded the number of 8.6. The technology is mature, but it can be further developed through the enhancement of the technology's efficiency and cost reduction.
- Tidal power technologies recorded the TRL number of 7. Most of the available technologies are at the commercialization level. There is a need for the completion of the testing of the technologies as well as cost reduction in order to improve TRL of these technologies.
- Wave power technologies recorded the lowest TRL of 5.3 in this report. Most of the technologies are at the commercialization stage. Prototypes of wave technologies are being tested in the relevant working environment. In order to enhance their potential to access the market, the technologies need to improve their performance.

This report shed light on several parameters that slow down the development process of the studied technologies. Some potential solutions to resolve these parameters are provided in this report. The proposed solutions are aligned with the SET plan targets, which provide a suitable guideline for boosting the development of the studied renewable energy technologies. When it comes to wind power, the SET plan targets call for the reduction of offshore wind power cost and encourage the development of a floating

foundation in order to enable accessing high wind resource sites. Regarding solar PV, SET plan provides targets for efficiency, cost as well as lifetime and quality of PV technologies. Targets for manufacturing and installation of PVs in Europe are also set in order to maintain the leading position of European companies worldwide. Lastly, when it comes to ocean power technologies, SET plan targets draw attention to the high cost of available technologies in the market and propose targets for the technologies' costs in 2030.

Insights for policymakers

The assessments of this report show that policymakers can play a key role in improving renewable technologies' competitiveness to access the electricity market. The findings of this study suggest the following policy messages:

- Creation of a stable and long-term policy framework, in order to encourage investment in renewable technologies in spite of their high up-front cost and variable power generations.
- The technology status in the market can be improved through resolving issues that make the process of receiving a permit for construction of a renewable project (e.g., onshore wind farm) long. This process is often long due to complicated legislation process or local resistance (for example because of wind turbines influence on landscapes).
- Development of market-based policy frameworks are recommended in order to enhance the competition in the market. This in consequence will curtail the extra cost that is paid by consumers and, consequently, enhance the CRL of renewables.
- Policymakers could contribute to the technology development by increasing social awareness about the economic and environmental benefits of renewable energy technologies. This awareness can reduce the barriers to receive permission for renewable projects or encourage society to invest and engage in them.
- Support the establishment of community projects, in order to enhance the position of technologies in the market and increase social benefits of these projects for local communities.
- Encourage and support investments in sustainable and reliable raw material resources as well as recycling facilities to assure the sustainability of renewable technologies.
- Support and invest in innovation and research projects that resolve stakeholders' concerns. Examples of such projects are supporting recycling facilities that resolve lifecycle issues of renewables or investing in the projects that study the influence of renewable technologies on the environment.
- Introduction of policies specified for immature renewable technologies (e.g., ocean technologies) in the market. The reason for this recommendation is that immature technologies have lower chance of receiving support when they are in direct competition with other cost-competitive renewable energy market.
- Enhancing public-private partnerships in order to bring together industrial partners, association and researchers. Through such partnership a stronger collaboration is formed and all the partner agree on concrete research plans and market decisions which result in a faster development of renewables and improve investments plan in these technologies.
- Encourage investment in cross-technologies that facilitate introduction of a more diversified portfolio of renewable energy technologies. An example of such investments is to invest in components that contribute to the development of both offshore and ocean technologies.

Insights for industry

- Industry players need to understand that the technological development of a renewable technology alone is not the only success factor behind their projects. Enhancing consumers' readiness, tackling social concerns or improving market parameters are another factors that influence the success of renewable projects in the market.
- Project developers need to set strategies and methods to enhance public participation in their projects. This has shown to have an influence on the success rate of renewable projects.
- Europe has a strong position worldwide in the supply chain of wind, solar and ocean technologies. Europe is the home for top wind turbine manufacturers, hosts more than 50% of ocean technology developers, and has the leadership of Solar PVs' equipment and inverter. However, these positions have been threatened with a rising competition from Asia. Setting the right measures and strategies can improve and maintain the position of Europe in the supply chain of renewables.
- Onshore and offshore wind and solar PVs are renewable technologies at TRL level 9. Tidal and wave power technologies are more immature and at TRL level between 5-7. Cooperation between companies could accelerate the development of more immature technologies in the renewable energy market.

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